

Oral Verrucous Carcinoma: an Overview

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Background: Verrucous carcinoma (VC) is a low-grade squamous cell carcinoma. It presents different morphologic, cytokinetic, and clinical characteristics. In advanced stages, it can infiltrate neighboring tissues despite slow growth and low mitotic activity, but it does not metastasize. The oral cavity is one of the mostly affected sites. **Objective:** This article reviews oral verrucous carcinoma (OVC) and offers information on its etiology, clinical appearance, diagnosis, and available treatments. **Methods:** Symptoms, pathogenesis, epidemiology, oral manifestations and management are reviewed. **Discussion:** OVC appears as a painless, white-grey, warty, exophytic mass that resembles cauliflower. It presents a strong predisposition for local invasion and a low predisposition for diffusion in neighboring structures and metastasizing. Histologically, OVC exhibits a well-differentiated squamous proliferation with a papillary or verrucous epithelial surface and clear hyperkeratosis, invading the subjacent stroma with well-defined, pushing margins. Minor atypical cells are usually seen. **Conclusion:** OVC is an uncommon tumor. To establish an accurate diagnosis, a comprehensive evaluation is necessary, particularly one that focuses on histology.

Keywords: Oral; verrucous; carcinoma; histological examination.

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1. BACKGROUND

Verrucous carcinoma (VC) is a rare form of well-differentiated, low-grade squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). It mostly affects the skin, genitalia, esophagus, and oral cavity. Oral verrucous carcinoma (OVC) accounts for 2–12% of all oral cavity carcinomas and mostly affects the buccal mucosa, followed by the hard palate, the floor of the mouth, and the gums. Various synonyms have been used to describe this lesion, including Ackerman's tumor, florid oral papillomatosis, Buschke-Lowenstein tumor, epithelioma cuniculatum, and carcinoma cuniculatum (1-4).

2. OBJECTIVE

This article reviews OVC and offers information on its etiology, clinical appearance, diagnosis, and available treatments.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Symptoms, pathogenesis, epidemiology, oral manifestations, and management are reviewed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

OVC is a rare tumor affecting the oral cavity; it is more frequent in patients between 40 and 60 years old with a male preponderance (2). Clinically, it appears as a painless, white-grey, warty, exophytic mass that resembles cauliflower (Figure 1) (5).

OVC presents a strong predisposition for local invasion and a low predisposition for diffusion in neighboring

Figure 1: Verrucous carcinoma of the hard palate

structures. Metastasis from OVC is uncommon (3, 6-10).

Histologically, OVC exhibits a well-differentiated squamous proliferation with a papillary or verrucous epithelial surface and clear hyperkeratosis, invading the subjacent stroma with well-defined, pushing margins. Minor atypical cells are usually seen (Figure 2) (8).

The etiology of OVC is unknown; however, tobacco smoking, alcohol drinking, and chewing betel nuts are recognized as significant risk factors (11, 12). Furthermore, other conditions, including chronic inflammation, ulcers, poorly fitting removable dentures, poor oral hygiene, and immunosuppression, have been re-

ported as causal factors (1). In comparison to SCC oncogenesis, the human papillomavirus has a much smaller impact on OVC oncogenesis (3, 11). Moreover, it is suggested that OVC may arise in potentially malignant lesions, dysplasia, and carcinoma in situ (3).

Although OVC is not thought to have a racial preference, investigations on Asian patients have shown that males are more likely to develop it, with incidences as high as 77.4% (10) and 94.9% (12); this may be connected to the culture of betel nut and tobacco chewing intake (3).

The diagnosis of OVC is challenging. In fact, it is very difficult to distinguish OVC from other lesions, such as oral SCC (OSCC), oral verrucous keratosis (OVK), and oral verrucous hyperplasia (OVH) (13-15). OVH has been referred to as an early stage or precursor to OVC and is believed to have similar biological potential (15). Additionally, many authors raise the problem of the differentiation between “pure” OVC and “hybrid” OVC, which has foci of SCC (3). Therefore, it is essential to differentiate OVC from all these lesions through meticulous histopathological assessment. Recent research has recommended using biomarkers to identify OVC. Since it might be difficult to distinguish OVC from other lesions such as OSCC and OVH based on the histopathological findings, Hosseinpour et al. highlighted via a comprehensive review the value of using biomarkers like Ki67 and P53 to help with the final OVC diagnosis (16).

Compared to other oral cancers, OVC has a better prognosis (15). The most often used treatment for OVC is surgery (3, 15). In cases of large lesions, radiotherapy added to surgery may be helpful (15). Other treatment techniques, such as chemotherapy, may be performed when surgery is not indicated. In fact, a variety of cytostatic drugs have shown favorable effects on reducing tumor size (15).

5. CONCLUSION

OVC is an uncommon tumor with a challenging differential diagnosis and an unclear etiology. To establish an accurate diagnosis, a comprehensive evaluation is necessary, particularly one that focuses on histology.

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Figure 2. Histologic features of an oral verrucous carcinoma: papillary tumor proliferation; acanthotic and keratinized stratified squamous epithelium; enlarged interpapillary buds growing in depth; minimal cellular atypia; lymphocyte infiltration

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